

IS LEARNING PLACE NAMES INTO GROUPS THE MOST IMPORTANT TASK

Jurayev Erali Xoliyar o'g'li

Graduate student of Geography Department of Termiz State University
eralijurayev0615@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article discusses the classification of geographical place names according to their origin. Several factors influencing the classification of place names into types are also shown. As you read this article, you will get a brief overview of the types of place names.

keywords: *Place names, hydronyms, phytonyms, animal, ethnonym, legendary names, strange names, modern names*

INTRODUCTION

Geographical place names are very different - district, and some names are very strange. Their origins are also very different. It is also very difficult to classify them into species. It is often divided into types in terms of language rules. They are also divided into types according to the stages of formation, formation, and what they are connected with.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The division into the following types was made depending on the origin of the place names, what events and events are connected to them. For geographers, it seemed more appropriate to divide into species in this way.

DISCUSSION

1. Names that appear depending on the geographical location of the place. For example: Nordkap (Northern Cape), Severnaya Zemlya (Northern Earth), Hokkaido (Northern Island), Southeast Cape, North Sea, East China Sea, Rio - Grande del - Norte (Northern Great River), Back Oloy, G' western Dvina and others.

2. Some geographical names arise from the specific characteristics of that place, geographical object. Among such names, there are many names related to relief forms. Ayiktog' in Crimea, Taurus (Greek bull) mountain in Turkey, Shpisbergen (Spear Mountain) in the Arctic Ocean, Iron Gate (the name of the gorge) in the Danube valley are among them. Our country - in Central Asia, there are many such names: Kumtepa, Egartash, Belisiniq ridge, Adamtash, Supatog' , Beshiktog' , Yog' ontepa, O'radaryo, Torgai hilly country, Chukursoy and Koytosh are examples of these.

The names that appeared due to other features of the relief include the Red Sea, the White Sea, the Dead Sea, the Yellow Sea, Iceland (Iceland), Mont Blanc (Oktog), Issyk-Kol, Kungay Olatov, Terskay Olatov, Bog Ishmael, Karakum, Karakorum, Windward Islands, Windward Islands, Polynesia, Micronesia, Melanesia can be given as examples.

3. Names related to water (hydronyms). The names of ocean, sea, river, lake, glacier, springs are called hydronyms. Hydronyms also differ according to the properties of water. The color, salinity, purity, depth and other characteristics of the water of rivers, lakes, springs and wells are different.

Rivers formed from underground water and seepage are called Karasuv and Karadarya, rivers that receive water from snow and ice in the mountains are often called Akdarya, if the water is clear and clean, they are called Koksuv, and rivers with cloudy water are called Sarisuv, Xuanhe (Yellow river) is named. Lakes with clear and clean water are called Oynakol, Kokkol, lakes with cloudy water are called Ayronkol, and lakes with salty water are called Shorkol, Achchikkol, Achchikol.

Tentaksoy in Fergana and Jinnidarya in Surkhandarya are so named because they flow during the spring flood, changing their course and destroying their banks. The names of springs and wells are often given depending on the characteristics of the water - temperature, purity, minerals and trace elements, and how it comes out from the ground. For example: Shorbulok, Kotirbulok (the water contains sulfur), Obirakhmat (healing spring with sweet water), Issyksuv, Obigarm, Arashon, Kaynarbulok, Jimbulok. Wells also have names such as Shirinquduq, Shorquduq, Chuqurquduq, depending on their characteristics. Small rivers that flow during the rainy season and dry up for a long time are often called Kuruksoy.

4. Names related to plants (phytonyms). There are many place names related to plants both in our country and in other countries. Names associated with plants sometimes indicate specific quantities. The names Orikzor, Bodomzor, Chilonzor, Terakzor, Qatortol mean that these types of plants are widespread in those places, while names like Yakkatut, Koshchinor, Koshtut mean that these types of plants are rare. There is ambiguity in names such as Nut, Kokterak, Toldikurgan, Bukovina, Beryozovka, Archakhishloq. It is not clear whether the nut is one or more in this place. Examples of names associated with plants include Schwarzwald (black forest) in Europe, Dragon Mountains in Africa (dragon - the name of a tree), Florida (plant, orchard) in America, Cocos Islands in Asia. can be shown as Place names associated with plants are especially common in microtoponyms. Almazor, Sebzor, Karakamish, O'rikzor, Bodomzor, Olchazor, Olchali, Karatol, Yettiterak, Bog' kocha, Chilonzor in Tashkent are among them.

5. Place names (zoonyms) associated with the names of animals. There are many names on the world map that are related to animals. By analyzing such names that exist today, it is possible to determine the places where some animals were distributed in ancient times. Maymuntokai near Termiz on the banks of Amudarya, Ghazalkent (gizol - deer) in Tashkent region, Bogistan (actually from the word Bugistan), Soqoq (white deer), Ilonlisoy, Kavtarkhana, Kurkuldak (bird), Borijar in Tashkent city, Kurbagaabad and others are proof that there were many such animals in these places in ancient times.

Such names are common in other parts of the world. For example: the Galapagos Islands in the Pacific Ocean (galapago - tortoise), where large tortoises still exist. Medvezhii Island in the Barents Sea, Big Bear, Little Bear Lakes in North America, Tushkani in Lake Baikal (called Tushkan in the language of the local population), Koplonyr, Koplonsirt in Central Asia are related to animals.

6. Place names related to minerals. Many place names appeared in connection with mining. The names of the cities of Tashkomir and Moilisuv in Kyrgyzstan, Kumushkon, Gazli, Tuzkon, Surmatosh in Uzbekistan, Nebitdog, Gugurtdog in Turkmenistan, Magnitnaya Mountain in the Urals, Magnitogorsk, Solikamsk, Apatite on the Kola Peninsula are associated with minerals. The name of the Andes Mountains (copper mountains) in South America, Argentina (Argentus - silver), and the Sea of Marmara in Turkey are also associated with minerals.

7. Toponyms (ethnonyms) related to the names of people, tribes, clans. Usually, the names of people, clan, and tribe are called ethnonyms in scientific language. Many place names appeared in connection with ethnonyms. Place names formed from ethnonyms are called ethnotoponyms. By studying ethnotoponyms, it is possible to determine which peoples and clans lived and where they migrated in historical times.

There are a lot of ethnotoponyms on the world map. The names of most countries are derived from the name of the people, the suffixes - iya, - istan are added to the name of the people to form the name of the country. For example, Albanian - Albania, Portuguese - Portugal, Dan - Denmark, Romanian - Romania, Bulgarian - Bulgaria, Turkish - Turkey, Afghan - Afghanistan, Kyrgyz - Kyrgyzstan, Tatar - Tatarstan, Tajik - Tajikistan and etc.

Not only the names of countries, but also the names of other geographical objects formed from etonyms, for example Malik Choli (from the name of the Malik clan), Baraba Dashti (from the name of the Baraba clan), as well as the city of Kyzil, Named after Erie, Lake Huron, Caribbean, Appalachian, Iowa, Delaware tribes. H.H. Hasanov in his book —Secret of Geographical Names‖ (1985) gives examples of 76 seeds that formed Central Asian toponyms.

Here are some of them; Adoq, Andi, Arlot, Arghun, Asaka, Bagish, Beshkapa, Boyovut, Bayot, Dormon, Yorboshi, Kaltatoy, Malik, Ming, Mitan, Mongol,

Nazarbek, Naiman, Nukus, Olot, Sawai, Sayot, Saray, Toyloq, Uzun, Chandir, Chimboy, Chigai, Chigatoy, Yuz, Kalmaq, Kashka, Karakhitay, Kuti, Kungiro. The name of some peoples, on the contrary, is taken from the name of the country. Examples of these are Indonesians, Australians, Brazilians, Cubans, Israelis, Palestinians, Ecuadorians, and Americans.

8. Names taken from the occupation of the population. Geographical names that appeared in connection with profession - profession are often found among medium and especially small (micro) toponyms.

Among them are the town of Khimki near Moscow, the Pakhtakor district of the Syrdarya region, the cities of Chirakchi and Dekhonabad in the Kashkadarya region, and the city of Qarovulbazar in the Bukhara region. In Tashkent, there are saddlers, shooters, knife shops, jewelry shops, shepherd's bazaar, blacksmith shop, town of doctors and others. Toponyms such as Orda, Khanaqo, Mahkama, Qazikocha appeared from the names of organizations belonging to the administration.

9. Geographical names (anthroponyms) given to names and surnames of persons. When such names are mentioned on the world map, we would learn a lot about tourists and geographers, explorers of new lands, research scientists who risked their lives to go to unknown lands, their deeds, written works, and heroism. Unfortunately, maps don't talk. But in such toponyms, the names of such people will be preserved forever. There therefore, when changing the names of places, if we don't know who the owners of these names are, we should not be too hasty. The names of Cook, Bering, Magellan, Columbus, Hudson, Livingston, Miklukho - Maclay, Barents, Laptevar, Bass, Flinders, Shokolsky on the world map are such names. The names of scholars who made a great contribution to the development of world science, culture, and spirituality, patriots who fought for the freedom and independence of the country and sacrificed their lives are forever preserved in the names of places. Such names include Beruni, Navoi, Ulugbek, Al-Khorazmi, Ibn Sina, Al-Farghani, Farobi, Pushkin, Washington, Jalaluddin Manguberdi.

Sometimes the names of heads of state, kings, tourists and explorers' favorites, even pirates are immortalized on the map. For example, the names of Queen Victoria of England and the famous pirate Drake have been immortalized on the map.

Names related to people's first and last name can be divided into memorial and simpler names. Memorial names can include the names of really great people, that is, people who are mentioned with respect regardless of the time and society, who served the entire humanity. Such names are preserved in any society.

Time will tell what names are memorials. Among the microtoponyms, there are many names related to the names and nicknames of individuals. But most of them change with the change of time, exchange with new names. Such names will not be

included in the memorial name. Chernyayevka named after General Chernyayev, Kaufmanskaya station named after General Kaufman, Skobelev, Frunze, Kuybyshev (cities) from the Soviet commanders are such names, and their names were changed.

10. Mythical and religious names. Geographical maps also contain names that have nothing to do with that place. Such names are created in connection with the characters of fairy tales, stories, books read by people, names of mythical creatures. Examples of such names are Takti Suleiman in Osh, Kaikovus stream in Tashkent, Adamota mountain in Sri Lanka, Shaytonmakon in Ural, Farhad rock in Syrdarya, Duldulotlagan in Khorezm, Shahimardon, Ali rock in Ohangaron. Such names are called legendary names. In fact, it does not exist - the names of places where the name of ku has been preserved are also legendary names.

The Land of Sannikov, Kohi Qaf, Yajuz - the land of Maguj are such names. There are many toponyms related to religion and the names of religious representatives, religious holidays. Religious names in the Uzbek language and Turkic languages in general are often accompanied by suffixes such as father, saint, grandfather, Islam, momo, nur, zia, sheikh, and in most cases such names are associated with the names of specific individuals. will be: Avliyoota, Zangibuva (Zangiota), Cho'ponota, Nurota, Shavkatbobo, Aksokota, Norakota, Surenota, Yalong' ochbuva, Islamabad, Sheikh Zainiddinbobo, Khojaalandorbuva, Bibi Mariam, etc.

In Western countries, words such as san, sankt, svyatoy are usually added to religious geographical names: San - Marino, San - Tome, San - Francisco, San - Salvador, Santiago, St. Petersburg, Svyatoi Lavrentiy, Svyatoi Nos and b.

11. Strange names. Some geographical names have a strange meaning, some are funny it will be scary. In the city of Tashkent, there are streets, neighborhoods and districts with strange names such as Khotinkoprik, Pushtihammam, Chuvalachi, Yalang' och, Koryogdi, Padarkush, Injiqabad, Jinkocha, Kallakhana, Kampirdevor, Qanqus, Mokhovzor. There are many strange names on the world map we will meet. Among the strange names are Krivoy Rog (Crooked King), Capri (Goat) Island, Canary (Dog) Islands, Labbay Mountain, Pocket Village, Zolotoy Rog (Golden King), and from the scary, scary names Dashti Lut (O' Names such as lim desert), Ajal Valley, Dashti Margoh (Death Desert), Borsakelmas, Dead Sea, and Jonchiqar can be cited as examples. If some place names in England are translated into Uzbek, they mean —Rahming kelsin||, —Blind grooms||, —Frogs||, —Zor Muhabbat||, —Rat Castle||, —Korinmai zhalil. gives nos. Many such names can be found in Uzbekistan: Kokdoppi (in Fergana region), Ogzikeng, Jojaogri, Kampirchikdi, Qorkomdi, Galcha and others are among them. Strange names have their own history and some peculiarity wherever they are.

12. Modern names. Geographical names, like all other things, change with the passage of time, political, economic and social, natural changes, old names are updated, new names suitable for the times appear. Everyone knows that Obruchevo, Gorchakovo Chernyayevka, Skobelev, Kaufman stations and others have been changed.

RESULTS

After the conquest of Central Asia by Russia, geographical names related to the names of the Russian conquering generals, the nature of the country, and the names of the Russian explorers who studied the natural resources appeared on the map of Central Asia. Among these are names such as Fedchenko, Korzhenevsky glaciers, Mushketov, Semenov, Ivanov glaciers, Peter I mountain range.

During the Soviet regime, the names of communist geniuses, generals, leaders and representatives of the Soviet regime in general increased a lot. The names of Lenin, Stalin, Marx, Engels, Molotov, Voroshilov, Chapayev, etc. were placed in hundreds of places. In addition, the names of communism, socialism, Yangihayat, Olga, Oktabar, Ilgor, Red flag, Red army, etc., which do not match the name and body, have increased a lot.

At the same time, the names of Alisher Navai, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, who made a great contribution to the world science and literature of our nation during this period, were mentioned. New contemporary place names have appeared, inappropriately changed place names have been restored and are being restored. Independence Square, Amir Temur Avenue, Babur Park, Alisher Navoi Park, Great Silk Road metro station and others are among them

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that when we study place names, their origin is related to various factors. The most important issue is to divide the current place names into groups and types. By classifying place names according to their origin, we not only learn about those place names, but also get interesting and diverse information about them.

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